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Australian Government
Department of Defence
Science and Technology

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE HOLOGRAPHIC ANTENNA STRUCTURES

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Background

ICCM22
MELBOURNE AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

#ICCM22

Multi-Functional Structures

Fuel Efficient

Aerodynamically Efficient

Structurally Efficient

Multi-functional Structures (i.e. SWASS)

Lightweight

Conformal Load-Bearing Smart Skins (CLSS)

Future Direction to Realise CLSS

Future Direction to Realise CLSS

1. Design an System (Active, Passive, RF, Digital, etc.)

2. Manufacture System on Pre-Pregs

3. Roll and Store in Freezer

4. Defrost and Apply

Conformal Load-Bearing Antennas (CLAS)

Conformal Load-Bearing Antennas – ESA CLAS

- Egyptian Axe Dipole Design
 - Electrically small antenna!
 - 300 MHz Operating Frequency ($\lambda = 1$ m)
 - 150 mm Diameter $\sim \lambda/7$

- Egyptian Axe Dipole Manufacture
 - Rohacell HF Core
 - GFRP skins
 - Copper, Veil and Embroidery compared – Identical Performance

Conformal Load-Bearing Antennas - Challenges

- Challenges with CLAS
 - Typically required 3D radiating structures
 - Suitable planar antennas are bandwidth limited (narrow-band) – typically aperture antennas
 - Passive narrow-band antennas generally require tuning post manufacture (i.e. machining)

- Desired Properties
 - 2D Geometry
 - Broadband/Wideband performance
 - Single Ply Implementation
 - High Gain / Efficiency
 - Composite Manufacturing Compatible
 - Easy to Design

Holographic Antennas – A possible solution !!! 😊

Optical holographic image invented by Dennis Gabor (1942)

Manufactured K-Band antenna – 24 - 26 GHz

Basics of Scaler Holographic Antennas

$$(\psi_{obj}\psi_{ref}^*)\psi_{ref} = \psi_{obj}|\psi_{ref}|^2$$

Meta-Surface Unit-Cell Definition

290 gms E-Glass/Epoxy Pre-Preg
 $\epsilon_r = 4.26$, $\text{Tan}\delta = 0.0276$ @ 10GHz

$R = 2 \text{ mm}$
 $g = 0.2 \text{ mm}$

$g = 1.5 \text{ mm}$

Meta-Surface Unit-Cell Properties

Dispersion Diagram

— 0.2 mm — 1.5 mm — Light Line - - $n_{eff} = 2$

Effective Surface Impedance

— 0.2 mm — 1.5 mm

Composite AIS Design and Manufacture

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Beam Direction 45 deg.

Questions